

An effective macro to analyze non-normal data with missing values

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Abstract

Multiple imputation (MI) is a popular experimental procedure for handling missing data, while robust regression implements novel empirical evidence for the decision regarding non-normal or normal variables. By down-weighting the influence of outliers, Robust regression minimize residual impact on the coefficient estimates. A macro developed by the Fortrea Company, combines two methods together to accurately capture this relationship in continuous efficacy laboratory data and protect against potential non-normality/outliers in the original or imputed dataset. This paper provides an example programming procedure and suggests possible improvements in the macro based on the author's experience.

Keywords: Multiple Imputation, Missing Values, Robust Regression.

Introduction

Robust regression addresses some limitations of traditional parametric and non-parametric methods in the underlying data-generating process, extending regression analysis to be less affected by assumption violations. It offers significant benefits in two main areas. First, it reduces heteroscedasticity by allowing the variance to depend on variables while assuming a constant error term, which aligns with many real-world scenarios. Second, robust regression effectively handles outliers. Traditional least squares estimation can be inefficient and biased when outliers deviate from the main data-generating process. While outliers are not always detrimental, especially in clinical trials, least-squares predictions lose precision as the variance of the estimates increases without masking outliers. In practical situations, missing values often complicate these problems. Multiple Imputation (MI) addresses missing data issues by increasing the available information for analysis, enhancing efficiency, and reducing standard errors. Many scientific papers address these issues separately, but the pharmaceutical industry increasingly requires an efficient macro to handle these complex questions.

Macro Variables Description

Displayed Macro

```
%macro NORM_MIROBREG(paramcd =  
,listvis = &Def_listvis.  
,keepvis =  
,nImpute = 10000.
```

```
,seed1 = &Def_seed1.  
,seed2 = &Def_seed2.  
,normtest = &normtest.  
,estimate = &estimate)
```

The macro program provides an automated and standardized approach to perform multiple imputations followed by robust regression analyses on continuous efficacy data that are expected to have a non-normal distribution. The primary variables in the macro include PARAMCD, which denotes the variables to be analyzed, and LISTVIS, which specifies a list of certain time points relevant for both the dummy dataset and the robust regression time points. KEEPVIS allows for the selection of customized time points for analysis. NIMPUTE represents the number of imputations in PROC MI, with a default value of 10,000. SEED1 and SEED2 set traceable values to control the simulation results, ensuring reproducibility. NORMTEST defines the methods to normalize the data once it is determined to be non-normal. Lastly, ESTIMATE specifies the type of estimate used in robust regression, defaulting to M-estimate, though other options are available.

Dataset Preparation

Dataset preparation is the initial step in the macro, as the real dataset might not present each observation at every time point, necessitating the clarification of missing values in sequence. This collectability issue frequently arises in clinical trial reporting tables, such as those for physical examinations, demographic characteristics, and efficacy measures. Dummy datasets provide a framework for the dataset, offering an effective method to establish the sequence and enhance programming efficiency. [1].

```
DATA dummy;  
DO &listvis = 1 to %length(%scan(&listvis,&i)) ;  
DO listval = 1 to %length(%scan(&listval,&j));  
Output;  
END;  
END;  
RUN;
```

Dataset preparation is the initial step in the macro, as the real dataset might not present each observation at every time point, necessitating the clarification of missing values in sequence. This collectability issue frequently arises in clinical trial reporting tables, such as those for physical examinations, demographic characteristics, and efficacy measures. Dummy datasets provide a framework for the dataset, offering an effective method to establish the sequence and enhance programming efficiency. Additionally, the dataset preparation process includes data transformation, as multiple imputation procedures assume normal data distribution. Many clinical trial variables are non-normal, particularly binary or categorical variables with missing values[2], which may introduce bias. Log transformation is the default method for addressing these values, and normality is tested before proceeding to multiple imputations. These procedures[15] manage missing data effectively and support the "Missing at Random" assumption, thereby justifying the analysis. Through these transformations and normality examinations, the dataset can avoid bias and be appropriately prepared for multiple imputation analyses.

Multiple Imputation

In part 2 of the macro, the design is based on Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods, which aim to explore the equilibrium distributions of interacting molecules within the structured data created in part 1. The replaceable values for missing data, generated through MCMC, rely on the pseudorandom number seeds "seed1" and "seed2". These seeds facilitate the calculation based on multidimensional or other posterior probability distributions via Markov chains. This method provides one-by-one replacement values for missing data, with each subsequent value derived from a customized posterior probability distribution. After repeatedly simulating "nStepMI" steps of the chain, the simulation-based estimates from this part are prepared for robust regression in part 3.

A detailed procedure for this part is divided into two steps: the imputation (I-step) and the posterior (P-step). The I-step generates chain-style replaceable values for the missing data independently, using the estimated mean vector and covariance matrix. With the current parameter estimate $\theta^{(t)}$ at the t -th iteration, the I-step draws $Y_{mis}^{(t+1)}$ from $p(Y_{mis}|Y_{obs}, \theta^{(t)})$. The P-step simulates the posterior population mean vector and covariance matrix from the complete sample estimates, drawing $\theta^{(t+1)}$ from $p(\theta|Y_{obs}, Y_{mis}^{(t+1)})$. This process ultimately converges in distribution to $p(Y_{mis}, \theta | Y_{obs})$. This convergence occurs from the Markov chain sequence $(Y_{mis}^{(1)}, \theta^{(1)}), (Y_{mis}^{(2)}, \theta^{(2)}), \dots$. In the macro, it calculates the mean vector for a nearly singular covariance matrix, with a noninformative prior set by default. However, in practice, the macro adjusts its prior to enhance accuracy based on data exploration[12].

```
proc mi data=Effdata1 out=miout1 nimpute=&nImpute seed=&seed1 minmaxiter=&iter noprint ;
var &treatment &stratification &listval;
monotone reg(&treatment)
regpmm(&dependentvar= &listval);
&transform;
run;
```

The function part creates multiple imputation efficiency $\lambda = \frac{r+2/(v_m+3)}{r+1}$, and produce such an efficiency table [17]. While r is called the relative increase in variance due to nonresponse [11], v_m is degrees of freedom and v_m is imputation estimator. Since most of time the "iter" higher than 20, default 10000, the macro achieves a better result.

1 Robust Regression

When the structured data fulfils the assumption of robust regression, the estimate will be based on a model that could achieve high breakdown point [4] or high efficiency or both [6].

$$\delta^*(z, T) = \min_{1 \leq m \leq n} \left\{ \frac{m}{n} : \text{sup}_z \|T(z') - T(z)\| = \infty \right\}$$

where δ^* is the finite sample breakdown point, z is any sample, and $T(z)$ is the estimate of the parameter β . Firstly, compute an initial consistent estimate $\hat{\beta}_0$ with high breakdown point with new structured data from part 2. Secondly, compute a robust estimate, defaultly M-estimate, of scale $\hat{\sigma}$ of the residuals based on the initial estimate. Thirdly, repeat the two steps before until find an $\hat{\beta}$ starting at $\hat{\beta}_0$. The optional robust regression types in the macro as "estimate" are M-estimate [17] $\hat{\beta} = \text{argmin}_{\beta} \sum_{i=1}^n \rho\left(\frac{y_i - x_i^T \beta}{\hat{\sigma}}\right)$, LMS

estimate [13] $\hat{\beta} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\beta} \operatorname{Med}\{y_i - x_i^T(\beta)\}$, LTS estimate [10] $\hat{\beta} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\beta} \sum_{i=1}^q r(i)(\beta)^2$, S estimate [9] $\hat{\beta} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\beta} \hat{\sigma}(r_1(\beta), \dots, r_n(\beta))$, GS-estimate [3] $\hat{\beta} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\beta} \sup\{S > 0; (\frac{n}{2}^{-1} \sum_{i < j} \rho(\frac{r_i - r_j}{S}) \geq k_{n,p})\}$. Different types of robust regression will provide multiple choice to get regression into convergence.

```
proc robustreg data=_eff_dataRobReg itprint;
by &cat avisitn _imputation_;
model aval = intercept &varbase &listdummy / noint;
output out=_eff_RobReg_AdjMean(where=(usubjid = " ")) p=estimate stdp=StdErr;
ods output IterHistory=_eff_IterHistory;
run;
```

Conclusions

The NORM MIROBREG macro offers an efficient and standardized solution for handling clinical trial datasets with missing values, particularly those with non-normal distributions. By automating the imputation and analysis processes, the macro minimizes redundant work for datasets with similar structures and ensures consistent, reliable results. However, the effective use of this macro requires users to possess a solid understanding of the initial dataset structure and to select appropriate normalization methods. Additionally, users must comprehend the macro's processing mechanisms and be proficient in choosing the suitable type of robust regression to achieve accurate outcomes. When these conditions are met, the NORM MIROBREG macro can significantly enhance the analysis of clinical trial data, providing robust and valid results.

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References

References

- [1] <http://support.sas.com/resources/papers/proceedings12/089-2012.pdf>
- [2] Bernaards, C.A., Belin, T.R., Schafer, J.L.: Robustness of a multivariate normal approximation for imputation of incomplete binary data. *Statistics in Medicine* 26(6), 1368–1382 (2007)
- [3] Croux, C., Rousseeuw, P.J., Hossjer, O.: Generalized s-estimators. *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 89(428), 1271–1281 (1994)
- [4] Donoho, D.: On minimum entropy deconvolution. In: *Applied Time Series Analysis II*, pp. 565–608. Elsevier (1981)

- [5] Draper, D.: Rank-based robust analysis of linear models. i. exposition and review. *Statistical Science* pp. 239–257 (1988)
- [6] Huber, S.C.: Interspecific variation in activity and regulation of leaf sucrose phosphate synthetase. *Zeitschrift für Pflanzenphysiologie* 102(5), 443–450 (1981)
- [7] Huber Jr, E., Ridgley, D.: Magnetic properties of a single crystal of manganese phosphide. *Physical Review* 135(4A), A1033 (1964)
- [8] Leroy, A.M., Rousseeuw, P.J.: Robust regression and outlier detection. Wiley Series in Probability and Mathematical Statistics, New York: Wiley, 1987 (1987)
- [9] Rousseeuw, P., Yohai, V.: Robust regression by means of s-estimators. In: *Robust and Nonlinear Time Series Analysis*, pp. 256–272. Springer (1984)
- [10] Rousseeuw, P.J.: Optimal search paths for random variables. *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics* 9(3), 279–286 (1983)
- [11] Royston, P.: Multiple imputation of missing values. *The Stata Journal* 4(3), 227–241 (2004)
- [12] Schafer, J.L.: Analysis of incomplete multivariate data. Chapman and Hall/CRC (1997)
- [13] Siegel, A.F.: Robust regression using repeated medians. *Biometrika* 69(1), 242–244 (1982)
- [14] Tofallis, C.: Least squares percentage regression. *Journal of Modern Applied Statistical Methods* (2009)
- [15] Van Buuren, S., Boshuizen, H.C., Knook, D.L.: Multiple imputation of missing blood pressure covariates in survival analysis. *Statistics in Medicine* 18(6), 681–694 (1999)
- [16] Wood, A.M., White, I.R., Thompson, S.G.: Are missing outcome data adequately handled? a review of published randomized controlled trials in major medical journals. *Clinical Trials* 1(4), 368–376 (2004)
- [17] Yuan, Y.C.: Multiple imputation for missing data: Concepts and new development (version 9.0). SAS Institute Inc, Rockville, MD 49(1-11), 12 (2010)